

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANANYA bearing USN 1SU17EC001 has completed his/her minor project on “*Android Camera Car*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2017 - 18.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANKITHA KUMARI bearing USN 1SU17EC002 has completed his/her minor project on “*Electronic Jacket For Women Safety*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2017 - 18.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BRIJESH** bearing USN **1SU17EC003** has completed his/her minor project on “ *Detection of Humps and Potholes on Roads* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2017 - 18.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GAUTHAM bearing USN 1SU17EC004 has completed his/her minor project on “*IOT Based Accident Prevention and Tracking System*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2017 - 18.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms LAVANYA bearing USN 1SU17EC005 has completed his/her minor project on “*Brain Controlled Wheelchair*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2017 - 18.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAKSHITH R** bearing USN 1SU17EC006 has completed his/her minor project on “**3D LED Cube**” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2017 - 18.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHIVAN N KOTIAN bearing USN 1SU17EC007 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Cell Phone Controlled Robot with Fire Detection Sensors* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2017 - 18.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHREYAS KUMAR** bearing **USN 1SU17EC008** has completed his/her minor project on ***“Automated Rubber Tapering Machine”*** in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2017 - 18.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SPOORTHI SHETTY bearing USN 1SU17EC009 has completed his/her minor project on *“Automation of Robot for Pedicle Screw Implant”* in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2017 - 18.

Dean, SUIET

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Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VINAYKUMAR K bearing USN 1SU17EC010 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Automated Union over Touch Enabled System (AUTES)* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2017 - 18.

Dean, SUIET

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Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms WIFITHA D'SOUZA bearing USN 1SU17EC011 has completed his/her minor project on "*Artificial Vision for the Blind*" in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2017 - 18.

Dean, SUIET

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Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMITH V KAMATH** bearing **USN 1SU18EC001** has completed his/her minor project on “ *Application Of Thermal (IR) Imaging In Driver Assistance System* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2018 - 19.

Dean, SUIET

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Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANUSHA S PAWAR bearing USN 1SU18EC002 has completed his/her minor project on *“IoT Enabled Water Purifier”* in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2018 - 19.

Dean, SUIET

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANVITHA K bearing USN 1SU18EC003 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Motion Detection Alarm and Security System* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2018 - 19.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
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Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms CHETHAN bearing USN 1SU18EC004 has completed his/her minor project on “*Solar Charger Circuit using IC LM317*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2018 - 19.

Dean, SUIET

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Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DHANUSH A UCHIL bearing USN 1SU18EC005 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Automated Car Parking System Commanded by Android Application* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2018 - 19.

Dean, SUIET

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Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GURURAJ bearing USN 1SU18EC006 has completed his/her minor project on “*Gesture Based Wheel Chair Control Using Kinect Camera*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2018 - 19.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HAFEEZ BASHEER MOHAMMED** bearing USN **1SU18EC007** has completed his/her minor project on “ *Teleoperated Multipurpose Robotic Arm with Hand Gesture and Recognition* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2018 - 19.

Dean, SUIET

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Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARSHITHA V** bearing **USN 1SU18EC008** has completed his/her minor project on “*IOT Based Smart Village for the Rural Development*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2018 - 19.

Dean, SUIET

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Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms PAVANAKUMARA S U bearing USN 1SU18EC009 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Arduino Based Intelligent Walking Stick for Physically Impaired Persons* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2018 - 19.

Dean, SUIET

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms POORNIMA bearing USN 1SU18EC010 has completed his/her minor project on “*Patient Health Monitoring System Using IOT Devices*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2018 - 19.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RIDA FATHIMA SHEIKH** bearing **USN 1SU18EC011** has completed his/her minor project on ***“Automated Soil Testing System for Agriculture”*** in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2018 - 19.

Dean, SUIET

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Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ROSHAN SHETTY** bearing USN **1SU18EC012** has completed his/her minor project on “*Dual Controlled, Solar Powered, Smart Pesticide & Fertilizer Spraying Robot*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2018 - 19.

Dean, SUIET

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SACHIN bearing USN 1SU18EC013 has completed his/her minor project on *“Wireless Safe, Smart and Secured Driving System”* in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2018 - 19.

Dean, SUIET

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SAHANA SHARIEF bearing USN 1SU18EC014 has completed his/her minor project on “*IOT Based Power Monitoring Socket*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2018 - 19.

Dean, SUIET

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VINAYAK bearing USN 1SU18EC016 has completed his/her minor project on “*Areca nut Tree Climber and Pesticide Sprayer*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2018 - 19.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DEEPASHREE bearing USN 1SU19EC001 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Automatic Effluent Treatment for Coir Industry* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

Dean, SUIET

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MADHURA S bearing USN 1SU19EC002 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Prepaid Payment for Utilities* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MANASA G D bearing USN 1SU19EC003 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Analysis and Classification of Milk Quality Using Electronic Sensory Organs* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MERWIN NEIL KUTTIKAL** bearing **USN 1SU19EC004** has completed his/her minor project on ***“ IOT Based Smart Public Distribution System ”*** in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

Dean, SUIET

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Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NAGASHRI bearing USN 1SU19EC005 has completed his/her minor project on “ *EEG Based Robot Control* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NOOTANKUMAR S MARISHETTI** bearing USN **1SU19EC006** has completed his/her minor project on “*Automated Human Activity Recognition in Video Surveillance System*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms POOJA bearing USN 1SU19EC007 has completed his/her minor project on “*E-Defense for Women Safety*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SUMANTH P S bearing USN 1SU19EC008 has completed his/her minor project on *“Sequestering Machine”* in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

Dean, SUIET

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SUMUKH bearing USN 1SU19EC009 has completed his/her minor project on “*Smart Water Meter Using Wireless Networking*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

Dean, SUIET

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Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHAYDEV SUNDAR V bearing USN 1SU19EC010 has completed his/her minor project on “*Electronic Car Ignitor*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

Dean, SUIET

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Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ADITHYAN J R bearing USN 1SU19EC011 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Digital Watermarking Device* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

Dean, SUIET

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Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADITHYU A K** bearing **USN 1SU19EC012** has completed his/her minor project on ***“ Intelligent Car System for Accident Prevention Using ARM-7 ”*** in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

Dean, SUIET

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Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKHIL S PRASAD** bearing **USN 1SU19EC013** has completed his/her minor project on ***“ Smartphone Controlled Quadcopter ”*** in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKSHAY SHETTY** bearing **USN 1SU19EC014** has completed his/her minor project on ***“Plant to Reuse Water Using Sensor Technology”*** in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

Dean, SUIET

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Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANAND C bearing USN 1SU19EC015 has completed his/her minor project on “ *The Smart Wrist Band Based Human Interface for PWD* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANJALI UPADHYAYA bearing USN 1SU19EC016 has completed his/her minor project on “*Smart Pulmonary Function Analyser*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASHIN RAJEEV bearing USN 1SU19EC017 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Smart School Van Safety System* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AUSTIN PINTO bearing USN 1SU19EC018 has completed his/her minor project on *“Solar Powered Smart Agriculture System”* in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DELVY AUSTIN FERNANDES bearing USN 1SU19EC019 has completed his/her minor project on “*Smart Safety Jacket for Small Baby*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DIVYA SOMAPPA LAMANI** bearing **USN 1SU19EC020** has completed his/her minor project on ***“ Smart Pill Box ”*** in the first Semester of the **Electronics & Communication Engineering** programme for the academic year **2019 - 20**.

Dean, SUIET

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Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HRITWHIK K** bearing **USN 1SU19EC021** has completed his/her minor project on “ *Artificial Intelligence Dietitian Using Android* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHAN M S** bearing **USN 1SU19EC022** has completed his/her minor project on “*ARM Based Smart Power Saving System for Home Automation*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NAVEEN KRISHNA K V bearing USN 1SU19EC023 has completed his/her minor project on “*Android Interface based GSM Home Security System*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RIDHISHA ALVA** bearing **USN 1SU19EC024** has completed his/her minor project on “ *Advance Energy Management Using GSM Technology* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2019 - 20.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AISHWARYA M BETTIN**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC001** has completed his/her minor project on “ *Piezo-Electric Energy Harvesting and Management in WSN* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKSHAR KUMAR SHETTY

bearing USN 1SU20EC002 has completed his/her minor project on “*A Laser Scanning Methodology for 3D Printing*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMARGEETH**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC003** has completed his/her minor project on “*DIY Segway*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GAGAN V

bearing USN 1SU20EC004 has completed his/her minor project on “*SmartSur: Smart Video SURveillance System*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GANESH VISHWANATH BHAT**

bearing USN 1SU20EC005 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Dynamic Car Parking Negotiation And Guidance Using An Agent-Based Platform* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HIMASHREE PRIYA M**

bearing USN 1SU20EC006 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Monitor and Control of Greenhouse Environment* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JOSEPH N K**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC007** has completed his/her minor project on “***VHDL Modelling of Glue Logic of 1553b Interface Board***” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MALCOM D SOUZA**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC008** has completed his/her minor project on “*Weather Station*”
in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for
the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

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Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms S L ROHITHKUMAR

bearing USN 1SU20EC009 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Blind navigation system using RFID for indoor environments* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAYEEDA SHAFaq ALAM**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC010** has completed his/her minor project on “ *Cell Phone Operated Robot* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

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Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHIVAPRIYA MAHESH KORI**

bearing USN 1SU20EC011 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Traffic Light Control System* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

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Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SRUJAN ACHAR**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC012** has completed his/her minor project on “*A Bi-directional Visitors Counter*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

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Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SWASTHIK NAYAK**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC013** has completed his/her minor project on “***Bomb Detection Robotics Using Embedded Controller***” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDULLAH AKBAR P**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC014** has completed his/her minor project on “*Telephone Router*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

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Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHAY Y RAO

bearing USN 1SU20EC015 has completed his/her minor project on “*Intelligent Alcohol Detection System for CAR*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHIN RAI B**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC016** has completed his/her minor project on “ **Centrally Controlled Multichannel Token Display** ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKASH V NAIR**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC017** has completed his/her minor project on “ *Microcontroller Based Cellular Voting Machine* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

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Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANAND ASHOK YADAHALLI

bearing USN 1SU20EC018 has completed his/her minor project on “*Two ways Wireless Anti Theft Alarm system for Two Wheeler*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANIRUDH S

bearing USN 1SU20EC019 has completed his/her minor project on “*Micro Controller based Security System using Sonar*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANVEEKSH M S SINGH

bearing USN 1SU20EC020 has completed his/her minor project on “*Frequency Counter*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AVINASH K R**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC021** has completed his/her minor project on “*Micro Controller based Burner Automation*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BIBITHA V R**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC022** has completed his/her minor project on “**Device Controlling Using TAPI**” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHETAN SURESH SHET**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC023** has completed his/her minor project on “ *Telephone Triggered Switches* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHIDANAND BABU KALLIBADDI**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC024** has completed his/her minor project on “***SPEEDES Qheap***” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
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Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DIVIN K R**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC025** has completed his/her minor project on “ **Wireless Motor Control System** ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

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Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FARA ROSHAN

bearing USN 1SU20EC026 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Card Based Security System* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GAUTHAM S B

bearing USN 1SU20EC027 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Microcontroller Based Barcode Decoder* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K SWATHI RAO**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC028** has completed his/her minor project on “ ***Intelligent Fire Sprinkler System*** ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KARTHIK D**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC029** has completed his/her minor project on “ ***GSM Path Planning For Blind Person Using Ultrasonic*** ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KARTHIK SAINATH SHETTY**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC030** has completed his/her minor project on “***Infrared Remote Control***” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHISHEK A R bearing USN 1SU21EC001 has completed his/her minor project on “ *A Zigbee Based Wireless Sensor Network for Sewerage Monitoring* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANANYA M GAYATHRI bearing USN 1SU21EC002 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Radar Data Acquisition System* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BHAGYASHREE DEVAREDDI** bearing USN **1SU21EC003** has completed his/her minor project on ***“Home Automation Using DTMF Decoder”*** in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DHINESH KUMAR N B** bearing **USN 1SU21EC004** has completed his/her minor project on "*Network Monitoring System Communication*" in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

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Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms N CHAYA bearing USN 1SU21EC005 has completed his/her minor project on *“Tanker Robo For Vision Based Surveillance System”* in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

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Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms PRAVEEN K J bearing USN 1SU21EC006 has completed his/her minor project on *“An Automatic Mobile Recharger Station”* in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHARANYA U SHETYY bearing USN 1SU21EC007 has completed his/her minor project on “*JPEG2000*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

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Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SUMANTH S bearing USN 1SU21EC008 has completed his/her minor project on "*Low Cost Anti-Lock Braking and Traction Control*" in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

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Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK KRISHNA S** bearing **USN 1SU21EC009** has completed his/her minor project on “ *Tracking And Positioning System* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

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Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADITHYA PRAVEEN** bearing **USN 1SU21EC010** has completed his/her minor project on “*Generation of Electricity from Wind Power*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

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Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANANDA KRISHNA NAMBIAR bearing USN 1SU21EC011 has completed his/her minor project on “*Automatic Over Speed Detector*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BHOOMIKA P GATTY KONAJE** bearing USN **1SU21EC012** has completed his/her minor project on “*Local PCO Meter*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

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Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FILISHIYA SEQUEIRA** bearing **USN 1SU21EC013** has completed his/her minor project on “*Micro Controller based Power Theft Identifier*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

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Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JNANESH KUMAR N P bearing USN 1SU21EC014 has completed his/her minor project on “*Micro Controller based Dissolving Process Controller*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

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Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K SHREYANK** bearing **USN 1SU21EC015** has completed his/her minor project on “*On/Off Control And Data Communication Through Power Line*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

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Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTESH SANTOSH NAIK** bearing **USN 1SU21EC016** has completed his/her minor project on “*GSM Prepaid EB, Phone Bill System*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

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Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms M CHAITRA RAO bearing USN 1SU21EC017 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Design Of A Color Sensing System For Textile Industries* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MADHURI ACHARYA B** bearing **USN 1SU21EC018** has completed his/her minor project on **“TENS Unit”** in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NAVEEN KUMAR S bearing USN 1SU21EC019 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Packet Analyzer* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIJA V V bearing USN 1SU21EC020 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Ultrasonic Based Distance Measurement System* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms PAVAN A bearing USN 1SU21EC021 has completed his/her minor project on “*Remote Vehicle With Unlimited Range*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms PENUGONDA NAGASAI ANANDA KRISHNA HANUMA bearing USN 1SU21EC022 has completed his/her minor project on “*Remote Controlled Robotic Arm*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PIYUSH P** bearing **USN 1SU21EC023** has completed his/her minor project on “ *Automation Of Ration Products Distribution System* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms POORNAPRAJNA P bearing USN 1SU21EC024 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Wireless Load Controller By GSM* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RANJITHA B N bearing USN 1SU21EC025 has completed his/her minor project on ***“GSM Unmanned Arial Photography Using Remote Flying Robot”*** in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RANJU K W bearing USN 1SU21EC026 has completed his/her minor project on *“GSM Digital Security Systems for Printer”* in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **REVANTH N** bearing **USN 1SU21EC027** has completed his/her minor project on ***“Sensor Based Motion Control Of Mobile Car Robot”*** in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SAKETH S bearing USN 1SU21EC028 has completed his/her minor project on “*Voice Operated Intelligent Fire Extinguisher Vehicle*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SREYAS SUNIL bearing USN 1SU21EC029 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Nav Multi Processor System* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET

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Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VINAYALAL H bearing USN 1SU21EC030 has completed his/her minor project on “*Digital Stopwatch*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2021 - 22.

Dean, SUIET